

**THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PARADOXES:
KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN ORDER TO
MINIMIZE IRRATIONAL AND
ILLOGICAL BEHAVIORS IN
ORGANIZATIONS AND MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract: The article takes a look organizational and management challenges in Nigerian institutions and argues for the need to create a collaborative framework in the areas of communication and innovative, effective responses. There is need for the practices of shared resources, competencies, and efficiencies. The article argues for the presence of a dynamic platform on which knowledge, skills, and productivity are spelled out. The role of leadership is emphasized in the areas of shared commitment and practicing and leveraging services through partnerships. The article recognizes the challenges in the Nigerian economy and attempts to state the significant values of cultivating best practices in the management of human assets. That is, there is a need for knowledgeable human to work with these resources in order to enhance best practices in human asset management.

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Introduction

Today businesses face various forms of paradoxes but how a nation and its economic and political institutions adequately manage paradoxes is essential. Seeking a context in which a business could fully carry what it wants or expects only to find out what it is doing is contradicting, creating tension, and in opposition to its aims is the essence of an obvious paradox (Van Buren and Safferstone, 2009). In his assessment of Nigeria's so-called economic growth in the face of deepened poverty, Odocha (2011) stated that the nation's natural resources like oil and other sources of energy such as corn and coal have brought little economic prosperity and development for the average Nigerian, possibly due to a lack of prudent leadership in many indigenous organizations.

In the book, "The 8 practices of exceptional companies: How great organizations make the most of their human assets," Fitz-Enz (1997) notes that as in life, organizations or human behaviors are sometimes irrational, confusing, absurd, or illogical. These challenges most often come out as a business attempts to cultivate best practices in the management of human assets, that is, human capital and resources. Other assets like equipment, money, facilities, or technology are essential but without a knowledgeable human to work with these resources the end road of that business is a set of hindrances and severe problems. One way to enhance best practices in human asset management is through benchmarking, which is basically knowledge sharing (Majed, 2005). To simply study, copy or practice the work of successful organizations in the absence of well-founded organizational theories, health, and readiness inside the company-in-need, is self-defeating.

Why?

There are process and contextual paradoxes in regard to how the company wants to operate and under what context its challenges are carried out. Realizing that there are visible and invisible forces that shape every company is important when trying to copy from some so-called best practiced companies. Also, best practices should be rearranged and be line with our present time and the current needs of consumers because of the constant changes among other resources (Bogen and English, 1994). Within the Nigerian business and organizational practices some of the current paradoxes of an apparent growth in the economy are employees and employers in a constant state of pain as they relate to poor infrastructure (bad roads, poor healthcare, poor power supply, and poor remuneration), weak communication systems, and heightened unemployment. These paradoxes not only results in manpower exhaustion but exhaustive management systems.

The effects of lingering dishonesty and poor governance in the society continue to result in serious implications for business development, management efficiency, and policy making. Nigerian organizations should begin to produce positive practices and evidence people/consumer-friendly behaviors across various contexts that in the end reduce employee frustration and enhance adequate management resources.

To minimize labor confusion and irrationalities in Nigerian institutions, especially in the public sectors, any form of growth in the economy should align well with a vision and commitment towards job growth and poverty reduction. There is a need to attend to challenges like youth education in terms of skills development, decreasing the level of crime, and poor work performance among

workers. In order for Nigerian stakeholders and leadership involved in national economic development and management to fully integrate the dividends of a growing economy from oil proceeds, there are some dynamics of transformation that need to be adhered to as they relate to being able to generate strategic and constructive benefits among employers for the working force and the entire national economy. Here are some helpful tips and need-to-know tasks for Nigerian decision-making powers and strategic management and economic advisers.

The eight driving forces in a best practice context

How should a company derive the processes and systems that could produce the context for best human asset management? In order to adequately transform and improve the human assets of a company, contexts characterized by the following interactive eight driving forces are needed:

1. **Need for Value:** The values of a company as they relate to human and financial operating convictions and beliefs are essential. The internal processes, activities, and systems must have connection to the company's values. This could bring balance in all areas of management and leadership.
2. **Need for Commitment:** It is important to set up a long-term plan and strategy, but without a commitment to the strategic plan inefficiency and ineffectiveness reigns. The integration of planning and enduring commitment is vital to success.
3. **Need for Culture:** For the purpose of efficiency, the organizational culture of the company or institution must be actively linked to the systems and operations. This will lead to the better management of the overall culture and environment.
4. **Need for Communication:** Information communicated must be wide, multidimensional, active, and open to the workers and all stakeholders. In other words, sharing of information among employees and stakeholders bring better productivity and management, as well as trust.
5. **Need to Partner with Stakeholders:** Building internal and outside partnerships helps the company enhance its human, technical, financial, and business values.
6. **Need for Collaboration:** The redesign, study, or launch of a new program should be done in a combined manner through collaboration. When there is a collaborative support within groups involved with all functions of the operations the company can build a solid foundation against attacks from the outside. In other words, making collaboration an ethic helps create a solid business.

7. **Need for Innovation and Managing Risk:** To enhance best practices in a company, the company should not be afraid to undergo a "shakeup," take bold steps, make new plans, or take risks. With changing times and unstable market or business place, well planned risk taking, bold changes, and innovation become important in envisioning the future of a company.

8. **Need for Competitive Passion:** Any company in search of best practices, improvements, and satisfaction should set up systems and processes that passionately and actively bring in good ideas from other sources.

These eight forces are equal among themselves, interactive in their own way, and collectively flexible in their respective practice.

What Nigerian leadership needs for best practices?

Best practices are usually developed through benchmarking and those companies that embrace the concepts of best practices (Creese, 1995) are likely to become efficient. These are ways to share and transfer knowledge thereby creating the best possible methods of business delivery. They are instructional, strategic, and workable models for generating good business and improving the effectiveness of a company (Fisher, 1996).

Public and private sectors managers should not be afraid of using and sharing good knowledge from better functioning programs. It helps bring in best practices. Innovative initiatives that could facilitate change should be done steadily in terms of time management. The management should be not only be concerned about the day-to-day activities of the organization but to also focus on the situational analysis that could lead to change. They should understand the importance of making changes in multiple forms. They should learn to reconfigure the institution or organization's values and philosophy with new relationships, business programs, and resources. They should understand that continuity of services means fostering the support of families and other agencies. They should learn to improve processes and services by shifting of resources, improving communication, redirecting funds, and using evidenced based inferences and practices that are essential to modernization and continuity (Alkema, Shannon, and Wilber, 2003). The concept of best practices is still growing in the Nigeria economy which makes it more urgent for entities to learn the skills in order to succeed in the future. They must to link internal processes to effectiveness and form a collaborative relationship other business ventures.

In our current business age, it is hard for any business not be fully involved in what could be called communication-centrism.

Communication is the lifeline of any business or organization and as a core task in any business or organization communication becomes a method through which management guides the attainment, exchange, and distribution of information. To be able to build an effective communication strategy that will lead to a valuable, multi-channeled or multidirectional line of information sharing, a company should have the intellectual assets or capital to transmit its business (Papa, Daniels and Spiker, 2008).

Management needs valuable or objective data to make sound decisions. It has to know how, when, and why it is collecting the data from the economic environment and from its customers. This process is essential if the data is to turn into valuable information. With intellectual capital or assets, management is able to use its skills which are knowledge-based, cognitive, and technical to ensure effective communication. This is important to both the sender (e.g., employers, management) and the receiver (e.g., employees, customers) in order to make the information result in trust, effectiveness, and finally into the results the company wants. The clarity of information transmitted leads to motivation and empowerment among workers. For a business to have value and be successful it must not be missing knowledge, motivation, skill, and capital (Fitz-Enz, 1997). There another side of data, information, and communication that relates to the value of information technology. An organization uses information to bring value, utility, and quality to its business but finds speed and adequate time management through the use of information technology.

Nigeria's organization's leadership should have a communication system through qualified staff and data that monitors services especially when they are not meeting the needs of the consumers. With adequate communication system in regard to innovative technologies, leadership makes it easy for consumers and employees to know its mission and culture. Leadership should be proactive in communicating with workers and consumers by investing in a multi channeled e-mail system that could send out instant information and receive instant feedback. There is a need for a system of professional development in various organizations to enhance personal skills, self-development, and helping companies develop an understanding of customers' needs, requirements, and priorities in the marketplace and growth in the areas of computer skills and organizational manners.

Nigerian leadership should learn to use information effectively in both bad and good times. They should learn to believe in a collaborative environment by celebrating individual achievements and communicating widely with all of its stakeholders. Nigerian managers and supervisors should learn to serve as intellectual assets in order to show

knowledge and demonstrate essential skills, including interpersonal and collaborative skills. Nigerian management should learn about face-to-face communication styles and help propel their institutions vision of educating and serving humanity with commitment and productivity. Nigerian leadership should know that with the advent of the Six Sigma concept, a methodology to help organizations develop an understanding of customers' needs, requirements, and priorities in the marketplace (Pande, Neuman, and Cavanagh, 2000), the old organizational attitude of every company to itself is no longer characteristic of new age organizations, especially in America. Organizations and companies now find it competitively advantaged by being able to garner support through internal (e.g., employees, customers) and external (e.g., suppliers) through partnering, collaboration, and modeling after the best practices. A Nigerian organization that has a positive and open alliance or relationship with its stakeholders leaves itself open to high returns and success. It is essential to note that partnership breeds integrity, trust, adaptability, confidence, and growth for all involved.

The concept of collaboration

Building collaboration throughout an organization creates a competitive advantage in terms of quality and performance management (Osher, 2002). According to Jack Fitz-Eng (1997) collaboration "involves working with people outside one's own section or department. The principal difference (between collaboration and other organization strategies) is that collaboration is most often seen within a function" (pp.149-150). Collaboration reveals a framework on which communication and innovative, effective responses could be delivered. Best practices organizations share resources, competencies, and efficiencies through an organizational culture of collaboration. Like many strategic interactive tools, collaboration is almost invisible and unnoticed but remains as a dynamic platform on which knowledge, skills, and productivity are spelled out. Often organizational culture, values, and leadership are created through collaboration. Organizational leaders generally maximize their impact through collaborative skills and foster collaboration through a feeling of trust in the company. Leaders build teamwork by facilitating the concept of collaboration as a value, a mindset, a position, and an activity of shared commitment and shared information.

The most important ingredient in collaboration is a sense of partnership. A collaborative environment must be one that allows an individual to perceive the benefits to shared relationship and working together. The value of a collaborative atmosphere is reduced

when arrogance, ego, bias, exploitation, and incompetence stifle an organization.

The concept of innovation and risk

Every organization that wants to become a best practice company should learn through risk-taking and innovation.

Nigerian organizations should learn about taking risk and avoid displaying poor organizational attitudes towards innovation. They must no longer prefer the status quo or the old way of managing business. They should embrace market and business changes with ideas that support holding onto aging and marginally educated employees who in the past resisted the use of modern technology. Nigerian leadership should learn to celebrate innovative practices in the areas of partnering with like-minded organizations. They should learn to invest in moderately priced technological systems to help improve information transmission, staff development, and training.

Conclusion

Nigerian leadership should learn to instill a culture and a climate where workers are comfortable trying out new concepts and ways of running organizations, even though it could be a somewhat costly venture. They must learn to set up a reward-incentive program (e.g., money and recognition presentations) to employees who demonstrate innovation, achievement, and collaborative skills. From a human asset and management point of view, they should lead the company's management and staff into training and practicing processes that could propel the company towards automation (e.g., in the area of payroll), shared resources (e.g., between departments) and toward the direction of leveraging services through partnerships. Nigerian businesses and leadership is surrounded with indigenous knowledge and resources that make true development among the people possible with regard to positive change and opportunities. The developed world and their people share the same goals for development as Nigeria; the only missing piece in the puzzle is the line of coordinated, integrated, and best practices for the pursuit of functional and sustainable performance in the organizations, institutions, and the nation in its entirety.

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